

Incident Delirium and Sequelae in Older Adults Admitted from ED to Non-ICU Units

Linda Ruhi Mahjoub, DNP, RN; Roxanne O'Brien, PhD, RN, CPHQ; Dana N. Rutledge, PhD, RN

Background

- Delirium can go undetected in 33% to 66% of patients in non-ICU units.
- Delirium contributes to clinical deterioration and non-anticipated admission of patients into ICUs.
- Increased lengths of stay and costs of care are consequences of undetected delirium in hospitals.
- Hospital nurses have important roles in delirium prevention through its early identification and management.

Purpose Statement

To assess, analyze, and report on incident delirium and its association with:

- Length of stay (LOS)
- Discharge destination
- Functional level
- Use of sitters
- Use of restraints
- Nurse observed and reported signs/symptom of delirium.

Theoretical Framework

Knowledge, Attitude, Practice and Outcome (KAP-O) Model

Method

Design: Prospective cohort study

Setting: Community hospital

Inclusion Criteria:

- 65 years & older
- Admitted to a non-ICU unit from ED
- English speaking

Exclusion Criteria:

- Critical care admission
- Non-English speaking
- Confused with no surrogate at the bedside
- Acutely aphasic
- Dementia
- Comatose
- Alcohol intoxication
- Taking medications that causes delirium

Tools: CAM-ICU, MOTYB, Katz, Charlson Comorbidity Index, Electronic Medical Record

Measures:

- Altered LOC at home (Y/N)
- Functional level
- Delirium (Y/N)
- Attention (Pass/Fail)
- Nursing documentation on observed delirium (Y/N)
- Discharge destination (home vs. other)
- Charlson Comorbidity Index score
- Use of restraints (Y/N)
- Use of sitter (Y/N)
- Falls (Y/N)
- Length of hospital stay (days)

Data Collection for 3 days/patient

Results

During the three days of assessment, out of 204 patients, 55 (27%) patients were delirium positive.

Incident delirium had significant relationships with:

- Altered LOC at home prior to admission ($p < .0001$)
- Functional level at admission ($p = .002$)
- Discharge to acute or subacute care ($p = .003$)
- Use of restraints ($p < .0001$)
- Use of sitter ($p = .018$)
- Length of hospital stay ($F(1) = 64.403, p = .003$)

Lower functional scores were associated with longer lengths of stay among patients with incident delirium, $F(1) = 62.888, p \leq .0001$.

Delirium and Discharge Status

Association Between Delirium and Disposition Status for Patients Who Entered the Hospital from Home (n = 201)

Delirium Status	Disposition			Total
	Home	Nursing Home	ICU Hospital (transfer)	
Positive	35 (63.6%)	14 (25.5)	4 (7.3)	55
Negative	124 (84.9%)	20 (13.7)	1 (0.7)	146
Total	159 (79.1)	34 (16.9)	5 (2.5)	201

Note: $\chi^2(3) = 14.86, p = .002$.

Discussion

- 27 % of patients had an incident of delirium at least once during three days of assessment, confirming findings from previous studies (Johansson, Bergh, Ericsson, & Sarenmalm, 2018; Kukreja, Gunther, & Popp, 2015).
- Since hospital policy did not require delirium screening, these patients had delirium unrecognized by staff in most cases.
- Significant relationships between delirium and LOS, discharge disposition, and functional levels indicates negative consequences for patients.
- The higher use of restraints and sitters among delirium patients indicates increased resource use.

Conclusions

- This study confirmed clinically significant numbers of incident delirium in the hospital.
- Delirium management is costly, and long-term consequences may be irreversible.
- Developing a multidisciplinary delirium management program may help organizations to manage non-ICU delirium proactively.

References

- References available upon request: [rughilinda1@gmail.com](mailto:ruhilinda1@gmail.com)